

Developing a Texas Hold'em Poker Bot using Deep Q-Learning, Neural Networks, to implement Optimal Game Theory and Exploitative Play

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Abstract. Poker, a game of skill and chance, has captivated players for centuries. There are many categories of the particular game, and within each there are many variations. Its depth lies in the complex interplay between incomplete information, hand valuation, and human psychology. However, the game which seems to involve the feature of 'chance' and randomness, can be analysed using a mathematical perspective. This research paper delves into the application of game theory, a mathematical framework for analysing strategic interactions, in poker. The paper will explore pre-existing solutions to simplistic models of the respective game. Through previous research in solving poker using mathematical processes, we will also attempt to approach the solution using game theory. We will also try to develop a simplified poker bot which uses Q-learning and neural network models.

1. Background Theory

For this study, we will be focusing on the conventional Texas hold'em variation of the particular game. Like the other variants of the game, it is played with two to ten players using a standard deck of 52 cards. The players compete for a certain amount of money, called the pot, contributed by the players themselves. Each player is dealt two cards face down, which are also known as hole cards. After that, 5 community cards are dealt at the center of the table face up, over several rounds of betting.

These cards are dealt in three stages: the Flop, revealing the first three cards; the Turn, the fourth card; and the River, unveiling the final card.

The main aim of the game is to create five-card poker hand

combination using the available seven total cards (two hole cards and the five community cards), with the highest value.

Figure 1: The 5 community cards

The table given below shows the ranking of hands in descending order.

Hand Rankings	
Royal Flush	
Straight Flush	
4 of a kind	
Full House	
Flush	
Straight	
3 of a kind	
2 pair	
1 pair	
High card (card with the highest face value)	

2. Game Theory Optimal Strategies and Key Concepts

An Optimal Game Theory Strategy refers to a strategy which strives to make the game “perfect”. The strategy makes every play unexploitable regardless of the opponents’ strategy. In game theory, a game with a set number of players and a limited set of choices (represented by the payout matrix), there exists at least one Nash equilibrium: a strategy set in a multi-player game where neither player alone can increase their payoff. Because of this, it is a stable point where neither player wants to deviate from their current strategy. In other words, no player can improve their expected outcome by unilaterally changing their strategy, assuming all players are also playing GTO.

Game theory often involves mixed strategies, where players randomize their decisions to prevent opponents from predicting their actions. A mixed strategy is one in which the player assigns a probability distribution over all pure strategies (the player will always make the same decision under given circumstances). In Texas Hold'em, this means players might sometimes bluff, sometimes value bet, and sometimes check, all in a way that keeps opponents guessing.

Exploitability

A key goal of GTO is to minimize exploitability. In reality, the size of the bet at a given point should not directly correspond to the strength of one's hand, nor should betting be limited solely to occasions when one holds a favourable hand, as such strategies can be exploited by opponents over the long run. Poker is all about beating the odds over time, hence it is important to realize that a strategy optimized for a single hand may not be optimal every time.

Balance

GTO strategies involve balancing bluffs and value bets, as well as other actions such as checking or folding. This means adding in a range of hands with which you bluff and not betting only when you have a good hand or betting a larger amount when you have the winning hand.

Limitations

Implementing a perfect GTO strategy in live play is practically impossible due to human limitations in processing vast amounts of information and the need for real-time calculations. This is because people might tend to make mistakes unintentionally in their strategy, due to having too many variables at play and not being able to calculate all the probabilities in real time.

3. Exploitative Play

Exploitative play in poker involves deliberately deviating from Game Theory Optimal strategies in order to take advantage of specific flaws and patterns in opponents' play. While GTO strategies aim to create a balanced, unexploitable style of play where no opponent can gain an advantage, exploitative play focuses on identifying and capitalizing on suboptimal behaviours exhibited by others to maximize winnings.

Understanding Key Concepts

The foundation of exploitative play is the ability to accurately read opponents. This involves monitoring betting patterns, timing tells, bet sizing, and showdowns to gather data on opponents' tendencies. Furthermore, once sufficient data is collected, players identify specific weaknesses. Common weaknesses include playing too many hands (loose play), folding too often to aggression (tight or passive play), or being overly aggressive in certain situations (hyper-aggressive play). Once specific weaknesses in opponents' play have been identified, players can tailor their strategies to capitalize on these tendencies.

For example:

- When facing loose players, tighten up the hand range and value bet stronger holdings, as these opponents tend to call with weaker hands.
- Against tight players, increase aggression and bluff more often, taking advantage of their inclination to fold.
- When playing against passive opponents, amp up value betting, as these players are likely to call but rarely raise or bluff.
- Versus aggressive players, utilize more traps and induce bluffs by checking strong hands, allowing these opponents to bet into you.

When employing exploitative strategies, it is vital to ensure one does not become vulnerable to counterexploitation. Skilled exploitative players meticulously balance their adjustments to avert other observant opponents from capitalizing on their deviations from Game Theory Optimal play.

Limitations

While exploitative strategies can be highly lucrative against known player weaknesses, they must be employed with care. The theoretical foundations of Game Theory Optimal (GTO) play ensure that a player cannot be systematically exploited, acting as a safeguard. However, the practical realities of poker often demonstrate that perfectly executed GTO strategies may be less profitable than well-informed exploitation of suboptimal opponent play.

4. GTO vs. Exploitation

While GTO strategy aims for unexploitable balance, exploitative play seeks to leverage opponents' specific weaknesses. Understanding the interplay between these two strategies is essential for any serious poker player.

Many players use GTO as a foundational strategy, only deviating to exploit specific weaknesses once they have sufficient information. Successful players often begin with a GTO approach, then shift towards exploitative play as they gather more data on their opponents. The key to effective poker strategy is balancing the unexploitable nature of GTO with the profit potential of exploitative play. Against unknown opponents, employ a GTO strategy to minimize risk and prevent exploitation. Against known opponents, gradually incorporate exploitative adjustments based on observed behaviours and tendencies. Continuously monitor opponents and be prepared to switch between GTO and exploitative strategies as the game evolves.

Additional Considerations

Game Format: Optimal and exploitative strategies can differ significantly depending on the game format.

Cash Games: In cash games, where the primary goal is to maximize expected value (EV) over an indefinite number of hands, players can take more time to gather information and make nuanced exploitative adjustments. The stack sizes remain consistent, allowing for deeper analysis and exploitation of opponents' tendencies.

In tournament poker: additional factors like varying stack sizes, increasing blinds, and payout structures create more complexities compared to cash games. During the early stages of a tournament, GTO play can be more important to preserve a stable chip stack. However, as the tournament advances, especially near critical junctures like the money bubble or final table, exploitative strategies often become more advantageous. Players may adopt tighter or looser approaches to capitalize on their opponents' tendencies, such as tightening up to avoid busting out or loosening up to exploit others' fear of elimination.

Psychological Factors: Psychological aspects, such as tilt and emotional control, play a significant role in both GTO and exploitative strategies.

Tilt: a state of heightened emotional frustration that can lead to suboptimal decision-making. Recognizing and managing this emotional state is crucial for maintaining a balanced GTO approach and effectively implementing exploitative strategies. Players who are experiencing tilt may become either overly aggressive or overly passive, creating opportunities for their opponents to exploit these tendencies.

Psychological Warfare: Understanding opponents' psychological states can enhance exploitative play. For instance, if an opponent is visibly frustrated or on tilt, a player might exploit this by inducing bluffs or making value bets against a wider calling range.

Emotional Control: Preserving emotional equilibrium is crucial for applying GTO strategies, which demand disciplined and logical decision-making. Likewise, emotional control is just as essential in exploitative play, enabling players to stay perceptive and adaptable without becoming predictable.

5. Poker Models

Now we will try to solve commonly known poker models. These demonstrate simplified poker games, which can be solved algebraically. Our solving will be based on the assumption that the games are zero-sum and are played between 2 players. The participants will be called player a and player b .

The cards are distributed independent and, the process is completely random.

For the models we will be exploring, player a is dealt a random hand $P \in [0,1]$ where P has a uniform distribution over the interval $[0,1]$. Specifically, for any member of the family, all intervals of equal length within the distribution have the same probability. Considering a 52-card deck, the probability of being dealt a particular card is exactly $1/52$; for the second card, it's exactly $1/51$, and so on. Moreover, the probability of drawing one specific card does not affect the probability of drawing the next card. Similarly, player b is also dealt an independently random hand $Q \in [0,1]$ with same uniform distribution over $[0,1]$ as the first player. For fair play, both players would be unaware about the strength of the other player's hand.

La Relance (Borel's model)

This model was developed by Emile Borel and is commonly known as La Relance.

Each player contributes an ante, a stake put up by a player, of 1 unit into the pot, and then they are dealt their randomly independent uniform hands on the interval $[0,1]$. Player a moves first, either by folding his hand, which means discarding their hand and thus conceding it to Player b , or by betting an amount B , ($B > 0$) which is added to the pot. It is to be noted that, if the Player a folds, he loses his 1 ante and Player b gains it. In the case Player a bets, then Player b options to respond is either by folding and thus conceding the pot to Player a , or by calling and adding B units to the pot. If Player b calls, then the hands are compared and the player with the stronger hand wins the entire pot, which is $2B+2$ ante. Therefore, the net profit earned by the player is equivalent to $B+1$ ante. If Player b folds then Player a

receives 2 antes.

Figure 2: Diagram of La Relance

Source: <https://scholarworks.lib.csusb.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1378&context=etd>

As the probability of the hands P and Q having the same value is 0, this particular case is not considered by the model. In the diagram the $\pm$ symbol shows that the hands are being compared.

Theorem 1 (Borel's)¹

The value of La Relance is,

$$V(B) = -\frac{B^2}{(B+2)^2} \tag{1}$$

The unique optimal strategy for Player b is to call if $Q > c$ and to fold otherwise, where

$$c = \frac{B}{(B+2)} \tag{2}$$

An optimal strategy for Player a is to bet if $P > c^2$ and to fold otherwise.

It can be seen that Player a has a starting disadvantage, as the player will bet with strong hands only and will only lose to a better hand which has a very small probability. However, at the same time he will not get called often by a worse holding. As a result, Player a will only gain just the ante. Thus, it can be seen the model is biased towards Player b . This is further proved by the fact that the value of $V(B)$ is negative.

¹ Ferguson, Chris, and Thomas Ferguson. On the Borel and von Neumann Poker Models. www.tomsferguson.com/papers/poker1.pdf. Accessed 18 May 2024.

Von Neumann's model

The model is similar to La Relance but, has a small difference. In this model if player a chooses not to bet the pot, the players hands are compared. So, this suggests that player a 's options are either to check or bet his hand.

Figure 3: Von Neumann model

Source: <https://scholarworks.lib.csusb.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1378&context=etd>

As it can be seen, player a who has an advantage in this game, and his optimal strategy is to bet for some $P < x$ or $P > y$ where $x < y$ or to check otherwise. Here x and y are some numbers. This means bluffing with the strongest hand and checking with the weakest, allowing us to make a profit.

Theorem 2 (Von Neumann's)²

The value of the model is

$$V(B) = \frac{B}{(B+1)(B+4)} \quad (3)$$

Thus, according to the strategy the player would check if $x < P < y$ and bet otherwise.

The values of x and y is,

$$x = \frac{B}{(B+1)(B+4)} \quad (4)$$

² Ferguson, Chris, and Thomas Ferguson. On the Borel and von Neumann Poker Models. www.tomsferguson.com/papers/poker1.pdf. Accessed 18 May 2024.

$$y = \frac{B^2 + 4B + 2}{(B+1)(B+4)} \quad (5)$$

For player b it would be ideal to call if $Q > z$ and fold otherwise where,

$$z = \frac{B(B+3)}{(B+1)(B+4)} \quad (6)$$

The model is closer to real poker since player a is allowed to check his hand and the player b checks his hand, comparing both the hands.

Example: Consider a situation where players play with 4\$ antes and 5\$ bets.

The value of the game would be,

$$V(5) = \frac{5}{(5+1)(5+4)} = 0.093$$

As B is equal to 5, the range of values for x , y , and z would be

$$x = \frac{5}{(6+1)(5+4)} = 0.093$$

$$y = \frac{5^2 + 4(5) + 2}{(5+1)(5+4)} = 0.93$$

$$z = \frac{5(5+3)}{(5+1)(5+4)} = 0.74$$

Therefore, the strategies for each player would be the same as the ones mentioned above and with the values found here.

Moreover, as player a is favoured by the model, the value of the game would always be positive regardless of the bet sizing.

6. Poker Models

Now we will aim to create a poker bot which applies all the basic strategies discussed above. Below we have included snippets from a code of a simplified poker bot made using Python. It combines basic rule-based logic, Q-learning for reinforcement learning, and a simple neural network for supervised learning.

Step 1: Defining a Poker Environment

After adding the required libraries, we set up an environment which involves setting up the deck, dealing cards, and defining basic game states.

```
class PokerEnv:
    def __init__(self):
        self.deck = list(range(52))
        self.reset()

    def reset(self):
        random.shuffle(self.deck)
        self.community_cards = []
        self.hole_cards = self.deck[:2]
        self.current_bet = 0
        self.done = False
        self.reward = 0
        return self.get_state()

    def get_state(self):
        # Normalize state: hole cards modulo 13, community cards modulo 13, and
        # current bet divided by 10
        hole_value = sum(self.hole_cards) % 13
        community_value = sum(self.community_cards) % 13 if self.community_cards
        else 0
        bet_value = min(self.current_bet // 10, 12) # Ensure bet value stays
        within 0-12 range
        return (hole_value, community_value, bet_value)

    def step(self, action):
        if action == 0: # Fold
            self.reward = -1
            self.done = True
        elif action == 1: # Call
            self.current_bet += 1
            if len(self.community_cards) < 5:
                self.community_cards.append(self.deck[len(self.community_cards)
                + 2])
            if len(self.community_cards) == 5:
                self.reward = self.evaluate_hand()
                self.done = True
        elif action == 2: # Raise
            self.current_bet += 2
```

```

        if len(self.community_cards) < 5:
            self.community_cards.append(self.deck[len(self.community_cards)
+ 2])
        if len(self.community_cards) == 5:
            self.reward = self.evaluate_hand()
            self.done = True
        return self.get_state(), self.reward, self.done, {}

def evaluate_hand(self):
    # Simplified hand evaluation logic
    return random.choice([1, -1]) # Randomly win or lose for simplicity

env = PokerEnv()

```

Step 2: Implementing Q-Learning

First, to initialize the table we created a Q-table with state-action pairs initialized to zero.

Certain parameters had to be set up, which can be seen in the code.

The list of parameters used are,

- Alpha: Learning rate, which determines how much new information overrides the old.
- Gamma: Discount factor, which considers future rewards.
- Epsilon: Exploration rate, which balances exploration and exploitation.

```

class PokerQAgent:
    def __init__(self, state_size, action_size):
        self.state_size = state_size
        self.action_size = action_size
        self.q_table = np.zeros((state_size, state_size, state_size,
action_size))
        self.alpha = 0.1 # Learning rate
        self.gamma = 0.99 # Discount factor
        self.epsilon = 1.0 # Exploration rate
        self.epsilon_decay = 0.995
        self.min_epsilon = 0.01

    def choose_action(self, state):
        if np.random.rand() < self.epsilon:
            return random.choice(range(self.action_size)) # Explore
        else:
            return np.argmax(self.q_table[state[0], state[1], state[2]]) #
Exploit

    def learn(self, state, action, reward, next_state, done):
        target = reward
        if not done:
            target += self.gamma * np.max(self.q_table[next_state[0],
next_state[1], next_state[2]])
        self.q_table[state[0], state[1], state[2], action] += self.alpha *
(target - self.q_table[state[0], state[1], state[2], action])
        if self.epsilon > self.min_epsilon:
            self.epsilon *= self.epsilon_decay

agent = PokerQAgent(state_size=13, action_size=3)

```

The Q-values are updated regularly based on the reward received and the maximum future reward.

Step 3: Training the Q-Learning Agent

To train the agent, we ran 1000 episodes where the agent plays the game, updates Q-values, and learns from experiences

```
num_episodes = 10000

for e in range(num_episodes):
    state = env.reset()
    done = False

    while not done:
        action = agent.choose_action(state)
        next_state, reward, done, _ = env.step(action)
        agent.learn(state, action, reward, next_state, done)
        state = next_state

print("Training completed.")
```

Step 4: Implement a Neural Network for Supervised Learning

TensorFlow was implemented for deep reinforcement learning algorithms. This allowed us to create a neural network that will predict the best action based on the state.

```
from tensorflow.keras.models import Sequential
from tensorflow.keras.layers import Dense

class PokerNNAgent:
    def __init__(self, state_size, action_size):
        self.state_size = state_size
        self.action_size = action_size
        self.model = self.build_model()

    def build_model(self):
        model = Sequential()
        model.add(Dense(24, input_dim=self.state_size, activation='relu'))
        model.add(Dense(24, activation='relu'))
        model.add(Dense(self.action_size, activation='linear'))
        model.compile(loss='mse', optimizer=tf.keras.optimizers.Adam(0.001))
        return model

    def choose_action(self, state):
        state = np.reshape(state, [1, self.state_size])
        q_values = self.model.predict(state)
        return np.argmax(q_values[0])
```

```

def train(self, states, actions, rewards, next_states, dones):
    target = rewards + self.gamma * np.amax(self.model.predict(next_states),
axis=1) * (1 - dones)
    target_f = self.model.predict(states)
    for i, action in enumerate(actions):
        target_f[i][action] = target[i]
    self.model.fit(states, target_f, epochs=1, verbose=0)

nn_agent = PokerNNAgent(state_size=52, action_size=3)

```

Step 5: Train the Neural Network Agent

Like the Q-Learning Agent, we ran 1000 episodes to train the model.

```

num_episodes = 1000
batch_size = 32
memory = []

for e in range(num_episodes):
    state = env.reset()
    state = np.reshape(state, [1, 52])
    done = False

    while not done:
        action = nn_agent.choose_action(state)
        next_state, reward, done, _ = env.step(action)
        next_state = np.reshape(next_state, [1, 52])

        memory.append((state, action, reward, next_state, done))

    if len(memory) > batch_size:
        minibatch = random.sample(memory, batch_size)
        states, actions, rewards, next_states, dones = zip(*minibatch)
        states = np.vstack(states)
        next_states = np.vstack(next_states)
        rewards = np.array(rewards)
        dones = np.array(dones)
        nn_agent.train(states, actions, rewards, next_states, dones)

    state = next_state

print("Neural Network Training completed.")

```

Running the bot

As of now the bot can be tested in simulations created by PyPokerEngine. By running it against different class of players the bot will gain more experience. The code can be considered as foundational framework for creating a poker bot using Q-learning and neural networks. The actual implementation for a fully functional poker bot would be more complex and would involve more sophisticated state representations, additional game rules, and more refined strategies. Testing and iterating on the model are crucial for improving its performance.

7. Conclusion

GTO strategy explores the concepts of balance and indifference which minimizes exploitability. When you have minimal knowledge of the opponent's play style, it is a good defensive strategy to play close to GTO, which aims to optimize for the worst case by minimizing your own exploitability. GTO strategy assumes an opponent who also plays optimally, or knows how to exploit weaknesses in any strategy. However, the assumption that the opponent is always perfectly rational and plays according to GTO strategy is rarely true and the discrepancy is what allows players who know how to take advantage profit. Even good players do not play a perfectly balanced game and open themselves up to exploitability in which case it is beneficial to play to their weaknesses whenever you have the information to do so. To play exploitative poker, it is important to consider past information about the opponent's overall play style, ranges, and strategy as well as what actions took place on earlier streets of a given hand. However, keep in mind that strategies that stray too far from GTO can be counter-exploited. Suppose we have two perfectly rational players who start off with very different exploitable strategies. In theory, over time the two players would learn to exploit and counter-exploit each other's' strategies and eventually their strategies would converge to near GTO. In conclusion, depending on the opponent, playing GTO may not always be the most profitable, but it minimizes exploitability, making it a safe strategy to play against any opponent.